

METHODS OF TEACHING LOGICAL THINKING TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS THROUGH LITERARY WORKS

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Abstract. *This article discusses methods for writing essays based on fairy tales. One of the main requirements for children is to embody humanistic values, such as love for their country, honesty, diligence, and politeness. Children who listen to and read many tales develop a broad worldview and form moral standards. Fairy tales provide not only spiritual nourishment but also guide children in becoming well-rounded individuals in the future. Students listen to a tale multiple times, enjoying and reflecting on its events before moving on to analysis. This analysis is directed at the students' conscience, encouraging them to engage with the moral lessons presented. However, pedagogical and psychological literature on character education indicates that a significant gap in the secondary education system is the lack of effective communication forms between educators and students, which has yet to be thoroughly studied.*

Keywords: *tale, folklore materials, children's literature, mythological world, psychologic and spiritual features, kindness to the mankind, scientific innovation, systematic characteristics.*

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, tales have nurtured individuals, particularly the younger generation, instilling values of humanism, love for their country, honesty, diligence, and politeness. Children who listen to and read many tales develop a broad worldview and strong moral standards. These stories provide not only spiritual nourishment but also help children grow into well-rounded individuals, serving as guiding companions in their future. According to the source of creation, tales may be of two kinds', the ones that created by people and the others that written literary. The latter ones enter the world literature and make up the majority part in Uzbek written literature.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS:

Among the foreign tale-writing authors are Charl Perro, Brothers Grimm, Hans Christian Andersen, A.S.Pushkin, L.N.Tolstoy and others who had made great contribution to the development of tale writing. The Uzbek tale writing has also a large history of its own.

Our great jaded (a new way of schooling system instead of the past) great grandfathers like Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdullo Avloniy, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy created a number of exemplary tales for the school textbooks they compiled, together with this Hamid Alimjan, Sh. Sadullayev, Sultan Jura's tale-writing traditions was continued by the following tale-writing authors like Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, A. Obidjan, T. Adashbayev, O. Imonberdiyev.

H. Andersen created his tales effectively relying upon the folklore materials. He tried to reflect people's dreams and unfeasible wish. He succeeded in making his characters and their live speech more complete. That's why all the tales created by Andersen are simple and clear to the reader. At the same time, they remember them for a long time.

The tales of Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin like "The Tale of Shah Sultan", "The Tale of the Fisherman and the Golden Fish", "The Tale of the Priest and his Servant Balda", "The Tale of the Golden Cockerel" are based on folklore materials and haven't lost their value for centuries and like that of the above-mentioned tale-writing authors have significant role in children's literature.

The great French poet and researcher Charl Pierro's tale "The Little Red Riding Hood" is still being recognized as the most favorite children's hero all over the world today. All the writer's heroes in his tales are distinguished by their love to work, by their knowledge.

The variety of themes in the tales also draws one's attention, various adventures, the descriptions of magical life, the victory of justice, glorifying man's qualities widely take place in them. In such work, particularly, applied arts, exaggerations are used again and again. For example, "In the Sweet Nightingale" tale the leaves and of the tree are of emerald and the fruit are of gold. But such magic taking place awakes no doubtful feeling in anybody. In magic tales the thoughts about the wonder things are also mentioned. For example, too much space is given to the descriptions of a mirror turning into a river, or a comb turning a forest. It appears that man's imagination is so boundless. It awakes the spirit of belief in future. It fulfills the task of main source in forming the characters world out book of his dreams.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As the famous and well-known folklore researchers state errors we come across most of all among different folklore tales are magic tales. In such kind of tales mostly the hero lacks something, the hero obtains the thing or goes on a dangerous journey, or pursues some kind of thing, then there appears a much stronger rival than he. Never the less these situations unite one another. The most important and dominating thing is the variety of themes, the magic fancy descriptions. For example, at the beginning of Hamid Alimjan's "Oygul and Bakhtiyor" tale is mentioned the lines "flying carpets by themselves", "Wings Tied to Fire", "Wingless flying horses" which just match the magic tale definitions, in magic tales the signs of mythological world outlook are felt clearly. Because in long olden times the snake which had been considered to be totem and semurg' (a table bird) and fetish which were considered to be the earth and the nations like the sun water becoming a tradition entered the mentioned tales.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the result the tales like "Semurg", "The Demon", "The Monster", "Mehrgiyo", "Beat, the Cudgel" show that the feeling of belief in fancy phenomena among the people of our ancestors had been high, Television telephone, constructions controlled from distance planes, the appearance of automobiles for the most part might begin as the result of dreams in magic tales.

As psychiatrists state children at the age of 3-7 get interested in everything and they are imitators at this age. Especially they try to act like the heroes of the film they had seen or act like the characters of the tale they had heard.

That means they acknowledge that Zumrad has got positive qualities. Sometimes when the mother's spoilt and naughty daughter badly colors her brows with us ma and if she is compared with Kimmat the mother gets angry. On the contrary whenever other girls are compared with Zumrad they never get disappointed.

The tale "Zumrad and Kimmat" enters as the Uzbek folk fiction tale and it differs from other tales by its educational significance. This talk is an excellent example of folk tale creation and the children hear it over and over longer time before coming to an elementary school. That's why it isn't difficult to write an essay on the basis of this tale for the elementary class's pupils. Therefore, it will be just to the purpose when the pupils are preparing to write an essay if the teacher will remind them of the plot of the tale and then tells his own basial attitude towards the events which take place in the tale. The plot of the tale is the following.

Zumrad is a clever work loving girl. Together with this she is affectionate to the animals world. As for Kimmat she is the opposite of Zumrad is an obstinate, spoilt and lazy girl. A proud and angry mother who loves only her daughter Kimmat. As she doesn't like Zumrad she wants Zumrad to leave the house. As the old man is a simple and quiet man the does what he is told to. As his old woman is an angry woman, he has nothing to do but only take care of his daughter. So, he takes he to the forest and leaves her there. The lonely left Zumrad will not be alone in the forest. And the wild animals will not eat her because always appears someone ready to help her.

By chance in the forest Zumrad will notice a burning lamp. On coming up nearer to the house she will knock at the door. An old woman will open the door to her, when the old woman finds out about.

Zumrad became sad after she saw their house from the roof of the old woman's house and noticing that the old woman made a presents kindness with the girl who always affection ate, thinks well of life and does good to all.

When the spoilt girl saw Zumrad come with the dear presents she also desires to have such things. But her bad wish, laziness, egoism spoil her life.

In the conclusive part of the tale the teacher reminds the pupils of the life's laws which are extremely complicated as every cause has its effect and according to Islam's learning "There is an answer even to the smallest kindness as well as to the smallest evil done" is written in *hadis* which helps pupils to express their thoughts rights and clearly.

First the pupils listen to the tale for several times and having enjoyed and checked the events of the tale they pass to its analysis. The analysis of the events is rightly directed to the pupil's conscience. They will see and clearly feel Zumrad's shortcomings. Because every feeling every expressed thought will be attentively reflected on paper.

That means in our taught pedagogical psychological literature on the upbringing of the man, generally the only lacking feature in the secondary educational system is the peculiar forms of communication between the upbringing and the and the up bringers has not yet been studied.

To make it more clearly the man's formation, that is his conscience, his mind, his feelings psychologic and spiritual features shouldn't be developed by stagnant notions and terms but it should be developed by means of basic modern scientific innovation which will be (just) to the purpose.

Important investigations are being carried out in this field by docent E.Eshmatov from Quantum Physics Department, Samarkand State University. According to him by creating the necessary communication with the information systems of the teacher and the learner on the condition that he, the teacher gets the skill by introducing necessary changes into his, the learner's inner energetic structure and only then he will consider his task fulfilled.

The essence of this idea consists of the fact that we can only make conclusions on the basis of things we have seen and they are proved. For example, different kinds of information and current energy changes we watch in nature (light rays, electric and radio waves). The inner energetic structures of these lifeless substances and effective current can be directly marked by means of physical apparatuses, whenever man's spiritual psychological changes happen within such small energy change space these currents are considered to be a too much complicated current to be controlled. That's why due to the outer effect we were used to value man's inner energetic structure mainly by their behavior, actions and relations taking place in the changers. For this

reason, we used to think that there were no laws between the natural sciences and humanitarian sciences.

Different unnatural phenomena (originally natural) and events which are connected with the spiritual psychological currents require their proof. As lifeless substances have inner energy structure in them. By means of effective mechanism on the inner energetic structure we'll try to make it certain in solving some dilemmas.

We made a suggestion to a beginning class of an elementary school teacher have one hour of educational lesson on the theme of "Water is the source of life". After a 45-minute lesson was over. We made a suggestion 30 pupils of the class go for a walk along the Anhor river. During the walk as we had agreed we distributed among thirty pupils a piece of sugar in sweet paper ask them to eat it at once. After ten minutes 10 minutes had passed, we found out that 11 pupils out of 30 threw the sweet paper into the water, 9 pupils threw the paper on the ground, 4 pupils held the paper in their hands, the rest of the pupils didn't eat the sweet.

Despite of just having had a lesson on the topic of "Water is the Source of Life" there was no effect of the lesson on the pupils. What mistake had we made? Usually there are some answers ready to give: "The teacher didn't have a good lesson", "The pupils didn't listen to the lesson properly", "The pupils were not attentive enough at the lesson" and some other answer.

These answers usually, can be based on one answer. If the teacher had chosen the proper method and made changes in learners' energetic structure then the educational current would have been considered fulfilled. The educational current within the space of the teacher's energetic field may be locked upon as the information changer current.

Usually this current is approached from the point of view of physiology and psychology and the information passes over to the main brain through eyes, ears and other senses, and the main brain and is commented by the similar effective means. Originally here the information change current that takes place in learners' and teacher's energetic structures is considered to be important. Here by all means there should be an ability of a teacher and a learner to implement the information changer between each other only in that case the teacher can make changes happen in learners' energetic structure.

The second carried out experiment can be an example to this. In this experiment can be an example to this. In this experiment we have repeated the above- mentioned case again. We have only recommended the beginning class teacher to organize writing an essay on "Take Care of Water". In organizing the essay, we have used from such contexts of tales as.

"The Droplet" (Tomchivoy), "The Cloudlet" (Bulutcha). The pupils wrote the essay on the basis of tales for 45 minutes. Then they were invited to go for a walk again.

Having finished the experiment, we watched the scene from the secret camera. The results are as follows: One pupil out of 30 threw the sweet paper into the water. 4 pupils threw the sweet papers into the litter basket standing not far from them: the remained sweet papers were kept in the pupils' hands.

The results were good. The reason for this was the teacher's appropriate information about the way of penetration the learners' energetic structure. It was to analyze and synthesize over and over the events by means of writing essays. At this their attitude was also added to the current. The most important thing of the problem was that tales were the easiest and most simple way of capturing the children's minds. You cannot find a boy or a girl who wouldn't like to hear tales. If that is, the way the information program being given in the form of news or given in the form of

tale context by means of pupils writing essays and by analyzing the tale's context it will serve as a means of solving the dilemma.

The reason, has also shoved the result of education and upbringing.

Through the development of essay writing skills originally begins at elements can be watched still at the pre-school education period. Whenever a child starts speaking, he gets interested in objects, in the world around him and in objective reality, "what is it?", "why can a plane fly?", "Where does the sun rise from?" and the like questions begin arising. He would try to find answers to them. While looking for the answers to the questions partly he will develop his attitude towards them. Gust this same current is the child's wish to express his own personal view arise like the first essay writing buds.

An essay writing together with the pupil's individual thinking and it develops their world outlook and makes education and upbringing significant. They play an important role especially with the small age children in writing essays on the basis of the tale contexts. In choosing the theme of the context it is effective to use small sized tales.

Tales may be considered like magic tools which make one enter the deepest layers of the child's inner world where original changes are made.

Only one should know how to use these tools, that's all.

Drawing a conclusion, we can say that to change the systematic characteristics in the man's inner energetic structure is to make changes in man's character, in his inner world. Relying upon the scientific conclusions and experiments invisible spiritual psychologic changes that take place in man require original research to be carried out. The analysis and results show that man's life is based on a certain successive law and it is based on the directions that may bring kindness to the mankind.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, one of the main requirements for children is to embody humanistic values, such as love for their country, honesty, diligence, and politeness. Children who listen to and read many tales develop a broad worldview and form moral standards. Fairy tales provide not only spiritual nourishment but also guide children in becoming well-rounded individuals in the future. Students listen to a tale multiple times, enjoying and reflecting on its events before moving on to analysis. This analysis is directed at the students' conscience, encouraging them to engage with the moral lessons presented.

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